

SIMULATION OF PULSED ELECTRIC FIELD BASED VEGETABLE FRESHER

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Abstract— The goal of this research is to understand more about the effects of pulse fields on food and compare them to other thermal food production methods. The most important factors for market demand today are food consistency, food safety, freshness, healthy food, natural flavour and taste with longer shelf-life. Pulse field processing (PEF) is a non-thermal processing technology that uses short pulses of high electric fields for microseconds to milliseconds to destroy microorganisms in food. It keeps food's flavour, nutritional content, and colour. PEF technology aims to provide high-quality meals to its clients. It can be used to replace thermally processed foods since it generates foods of superior quality to those produced by thermal processing.

Keywords- Food Processing Technology, Pulsed Electrical Fields Methods, Thermal, Compare, Quality, Electric

I. INTRODUCTION

PEF is a non-thermal food protection approach that uses brief electrical pulses to inactivate bacteria while inflicting minimal damage to food quality features. PEF technology aims to provide consumers with high-quality foods. For food safety reasons, PEF processing is preferred over standard thermal processing procedures since it prevents or considerably reduces detrimental changes in food sensory attributes. PEF technology aims to provide consumers with high-quality foods.

PEF technology has been regarded as better to other techniques of removing germs, such as heat treatments, because it removes germs while preserving the fundamental colour, flavour, texture, and organic process price of the unprocessed food. Adding high-voltage pulses to liquid or semi-solid foods sandwiched between two electrodes is required for PEF technology. PEF research has mostly focused on how PEF treatments affect microbic inactivation in milk, milk proteins, egg products, juice, and other liquid meals. While PEF has published numerous research articles on the microbiological elements of food preservation, there is less information available on the impact of this science on food ingredients, general uniformity, and acceptability. Periodic electrical fields (PEF) have recently reawakened interest in food processing. The PEF treatment has been demonstrated to be effective at inactivating microorganisms, boosting pressing potency and boosting juice extraction from food plants, and accelerating dehydration and drying of food. Non-thermal procedures have gained popularity in recent years as a feasible alternative to conventional thermal treatments due to increased

demand for foods with a high organic process price and fresh-like features. PEFs (periodic electrical fields) are a non-thermal food processing technique that has received a lot of attention. The PEF mechanism has been studied in relation to a variety of liquid foods by several researchers. Two of the most commonly examined foods in PEF studies are apple and pomegranate juices. Sensory characteristics of juices are reported to be preserved, and shelf life is reported to be extended. Despite being refined for a long time, yoghurt beverages, apple sauce, and sauce have been observed to keep a fresh-like consistency. PEF-processed foods include milk, juice, pea soup, liquid whole egg, and liquid egg product.

Food storage technologies have been employed to encourage the growth of microorganisms or to prevent their inactivation. Conditions that most effectively affect the expansion and survival of microorganisms, such as temperature, water content, the inclusion of chemicals like preservation, pH, and changes in the environment, are used to sustain foods in some circumstances. If the microorganisms are relocated to a suitable habitat, they will not be killed and will remain metabolically active and stable. Because the infection dose of certain moribund bacteria is thought to be very low, development of such germs in foods isn't required to cause infection.

A modern technique must have a significant impact on efficiency while keeping the cost of technology within tolerable bounds to be labelled an alternative methodology. In recent years, a number of technologies have been investigated that have the ability to inactivate microorganisms at temperatures lower than those utilised in typical heat treatments. The use of high-intensity, short-duration electrical fields, ranging from microseconds to milliseconds, can cause cell membrane permeabilization, either temporarily or permanently. The effects of PEF on bio membranes have been extensively explored, as the application of PEF has spurred interest in many scientific domains such as cell biology, biotechnology, medicine, and food science. The impact of PEF-processing factors on the bioactive composition of foods during their shelf life is investigated and compared to that obtained for various thermal and non-thermal process technologies, with a focus on PEF-processing variables. Furthermore, when attempting to maintain the health-promoting alternatives of plant-based foods, instances of both the promise and the flaws of PEF technology are provided. Electrical fields are used in the PEF technology to inactivate the vegetative cells of bacteria and yeasts in a variety of foods. This method is primarily used to battle food-borne diseases

and spoilage microorganisms, particularly in acidic foods, because microbe spores are resistant to periodic electrical fields. In addition to its volumetric effects, PEF technology dominates the microbiological protection of meals in a quick and homogenised manner. The unmatched application preserves the sensory and organic process price of foods for a longer amount of time without the use of heat. PEF technology has the ability to cut energy consumption while also producing microbiologically safe and minimally processed foods in a cost-effective and efficient manner. The effective use of PEF technology means that traditional thermal processing of liquid food products such as fruit juices and liquid egg is no longer necessary.

II. PRINCIPLE OF PEF

PEF technologies require the use of heartbeats with greater electric fields for only a few microseconds or milliseconds, with force ranging from 10 to 80 kV/cm. The contact is determined by the number of heartbeats sent to the object held between two anodes. A void known as the chamber's treatment hole exists between these anodes. The use of high voltage during the manufacture of PEF renders microorganisms present in the food sample inert. The electric field is used by a variety of systems, including drastically rotting waves, bipolar waves, and oscillating heartbeats. The relationship can also be expressed using several temperature scales, such as surrounding, sub-encompassing, and more encompassing temperatures. The food is stuffed and stored in the refrigerator after being treated with PEF.

Food is made up of a few particles that give it an identifiable level of electrical conductivity, which is the physics underlying food's electric heartbeat exchange. Because of the existence of charged particles, this technique is frequently used for fluid food types because electrical flow flows more effectively through the fluid food and the interchange of heartbeats from one highlight to the next is particularly easy in fluids.

In the fundamental framework, a heartbeat generator is employed to create high-voltage beats. The treatment chamber is connected to the regulating and monitoring equipment and handles the item to be handled. The food item is placed in the treatment chamber, which has terminals coupled by a nonconductive substance that keeps the power advancement from one terminal to the next. High-voltage electrical heartbeats are sent to the object, which it gathers. A charge is applied to the object placed between the anodes, causing the bacterial cell layers to burst. Milk, juices, yoghurt, fluid eggs, and soups are all often recommended for sanitization with PEF creativity. Combining PEF with ultrasound, high pressing factor, and bright light treatments can also increase interaction yield.

MICROBIAL INACTIVATION BY PEF:

Several research have looked into PEF's mechanism of action in lowering microbial burden in various food products. The particular molecular technique behind PEF's microbial inactivation, on the other hand, has yet to be fully described. However, the introduction of an electrical field and electromechanical compression, which induces microbial membrane instability and pore creation, is a general mechanism of PEF function. An electrical field creates a critical membrane potential, which causes membrane mechanical fickleness. When electroporation causes a significant increase in membrane rupture and permeability, this is known as electro permeabilization. Electropermeabilization can be reversible or permanent, depending on the degree of membrane organisational changes that occur during cell death. According to the literature, boosting the electric field's power greatly enhances membrane permeability. Microbial cell inactivation is linked to increased membrane instability. Spores are thought to be more resistant to PEF treatment than vegetative cells.

PRODUCT NATURE

Because PEF treats a wide range of things, including fruit juices, liquid eggs, milk, and dried herbs, the quality of the food has a significant impact on its administration. PEF treatment is unsuccessful for materials having particles or specific features, such as emulsions, according to experiments. The physical and chemical qualities of the meal also influence the rate of microbial decontamination. pH, water movement, and electrical conductivity all affect PEF's ability to inactivate bacteria, according to numerous findings.

pH has a significant impact on microbial inactivation kinetics. According to Jeantet et al., Salmonella inactivation is higher in foods with pH values of neutral or above neutral. In high acid foods like citrus juices, Alvarez et al. discovered a considerable decrease in the quantity of *L. monocytogenes*. In the same way, The conductivity of the care medium has an inverse relationship with microbial inactivation. Microorganism inactivation was shown to be lower in foods with high electrical conductivity after PEF treatments. Water activity shows a clear relationship with microbial reduction by PEF treatment, according to Min and Zhang.

CHARACTERISTICS OF MICROBES:

Microorganism inactivation with PEF technology is also influenced by microbial properties like type, species, and strains. Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, in contrast to yeast cells, are thought to be more immunological. Meanwhile, bacterial and mould spores are claimed to be resistant to PEF treatments. Cell size and shape have an impact on inactivation kinetics due to differences in the creation of critical membrane potential. PEF treatment affects different bacterial species at various rates. Salmonella and *E. coli* are known to be more susceptible to PEF than *Listeria* and *Bacillus* species. PEF quality is influenced by temperature, growth medium, nutrient concentration, and the pH of the treated medium.

III. APPLICATIONS IN FOOD INDUSTRY:

Pasteurization of juices, milk and dairy products, broth, and liquid eggs has been accomplished using PEF processing. However, it has several drawbacks, such as the need for the substance to be free of air bubbles and a poorer electrical conductivity. To achieve proper treatment, particle size should be lower than the gap in the care region. Despite the fact that PEF is not suggested for solid foods, several solid goods have been evaluated to see if they can be handled efficiently with PEF. Plant cell extraction of bioactive components and sugars can also benefit from PEF methods. PEF processing's ability to handle less viscous fruit liquids with lower electrical conductivity, such as apple, orange, and cranberry juices, is a big plus. PEF technology has a good impact on the consistency parameters of fruit juice. Similarly, PEF-treated foods had a longer shelf life and maintained their fresh taste, texture, and practical attributes in addition to their microbiological quality. In recent years, PEF technology has been employed for a variety of purposes, including speeding up drying, changing enzyme behaviour, solid food preservation, waste water disposal, and extraction.

PEF IN FRUIT PROCESSING:

The citrus industry could benefit from pef processing, particularly in terms of inactivating microbes and limiting the development of off-flavors during storage. According to Remain et al., treating apple juice

with pef enhanced the diffusion coefficients of soluble compounds. This method can also be used to degrade biological tissues in order to boost intracellular chemical production in a variety of fruits. Pectin, for example, is a very valuable component found in many fruits that is normally extracted via an enzymatic reaction, however this reaction is inefficient and results in less pectin being produced.

BACTERIAL INACTIVATION IN MILK BY PEF

Inadequately pasteurised milk can cause a variety of health concerns due to the presence of pathogenic bacteria such as E. coli, Listeria, and Pseudocodes SPP. Concerns regarding the impact of heat treatment on milk production, as well as consumer demand for commodities with a fresh-like quality, inspired the introduction of the pef for milk pasteurisation. Microbial inactivation caused by pef is regarded to be an effective way to preserve milk without losing its consistency. Studies have demonstrated the efficiency of the PEF technique for microbial reduction in simulated ultra-filtrate and skim milk. As a result, evaluating the pef solution's ability to inactivate bacteria in a dynamic whole milk matrix in a genuine comparison to thermal pasteurisation is crucial.

PEF AND MEAT QUALITY

Animal products are widely consumed around the world because they provide vital micronutrients and high-quality protein. Meat quality is especially essential because it is regarded as the most essential component in customer purchasing decisions. In solid meals, pulsed and electric field technology has showed potential in a variety of applications, including. The PEF method can be utilised in the meat processing business for a variety of reasons, including enhancing cell penetration to increase tenderness, reducing microbial load to increase meat shelf life, and conserving the volatile portion of meat during storage. PEF technology can help with enzyme release and glycolysis, which are both important for meat tenderization.

IV.EXISTING TRADITIONALSYSTEMS

SUGARING:

In ancient cultures, sugar was utilised as a preservative, and it was common to keep fruit in honey. In northern areas where there isn't enough light to dry foods, preserves are made by heating fruit with sugar.

FREEZING:

Freezing is also one of the most frequent ways to preserve a wide range of foods, both commercially and at home, including packaged items that may not have needed to be frozen in their raw state.

BOILING:

Boiling liquid food products can kill microbes.

HEATING:

Heating at temperatures high enough to kill germs within the meal may also be a possibility with everlasting stews. Milk is frequently boiled before storage to kill bacteria. Other options include curing, pickling, and jugging.

V.PROPOSED SYSTEM

The suggested system is based on the pulsed field theory and aims to create a composite bin. A non-thermal method for food treatment is pulsed field treatment. If a minimum field strength is required for electrification, improving the electrical field distribution's homogeneity is usually regarded to increase the process's energy efficiency.

BLOCKDIAGRAM:

The Block diagram is depicted below. The major blocks are Bridge

rectifier circuit, Frequency boost converter, PEF electric field generator circuit.

VI. BLOCK DESCRIPTION

CONSTRUCTION:

Bridge rectifier: The design of a bridge rectifier is shown in the diagram below. The bridge rectifier circuit consists of four diodes D1, D2, D3, D4, and a load resistor RL. The four diodes are coupled in a closed-loop design to efficiently convert alternating current (AC) to direct current (DC). The absence of the costly center-tapped transformer is the key benefit of this configuration.

The input signal is applied to terminals A and B, while terminals C and D are connected to the load resistor RL to obtain the output DC signal. Because of the configuration of the four diodes, only two diodes conduct electricity during each half cycle. D1 and D3 conduct electric current as a pair during the positive half loop. Diodes D2 and D4 also conduct electric current during a negative half loop. During the positive half period, when an AC signal is applied through the bridge rectifier, terminal A becomes positive and terminal B becomes negative. As a result, D1 and D3 become forward biased, whereas D2 and D4 become reverse biased. The graphic below depicts the flow of current during the positive half-cycle:

During the negative half-cycle, terminal B becomes positive, while terminal A becomes negative. Forward bias is induced in diodes D2 and D4 and reverse bias is induced in diodes D1 and D3. The following diagram depicts the current flow during the negative half

cycle: As seen in the pictures above, the current flow through load resistor RL is the same in both the positive and negative parts of the loop. The output DC signal's polarity can be totally positive or totally negative. In our circumstance, it is totally optimistic. We get a totally negative DC voltage when the diodes' paths are reversed. As a result, a bridge rectifier permits electric current to flow during the input alternating current signal's positive and negative half cycles. The bridge rectifier's output waveforms are displayed in the diagram below.

VII. SIMULATION RESULT

VIII. CONCLUSION

The composite bin has been built and put to the test. The experiment yielded positive results. The technology was found to be both cost-efficient and effective in its use. The ATmega8 microcontroller turned out to be a far more powerful operating system. We also determined that this method offers several advantages over typical heat treatments, including 1) longer shelf life. 2) The levels of pathogens are lower. 3) Improved pro. The technology of pulsed electric fields is being researched all around the world. The majority of the study so far has been done in the lab and on a modest scale, and the findings have been promising. The ability of PEF to eliminate microorganisms in food, reduce enzymatic activity, and extend shelf life while improving the consistency of the penultimate product slightly over the first is the foundation for this prediction. Food preservation methods are used in the food business to prevent germs from contaminating foods after they have already done so. The basis of food preservation technologies are the prevention of microbial growth or the inactivation of microbials. PEF is a simple non-thermal food preservation method that may one day replace standard thermal processing. When subjected to intense electrical field pulses, cell membranes develop pores, either by widening existing pores or by forming new ones. These pores can be permanent or transitory, depending on the therapeutic condition. There are more components in the pulsed electric processing apparatus. The technique of pulsed electric fields is being studied all around the world. The majority of the research to date has been conducted in the laboratory and on a pilot plant scale, with encouraging findings. Depending on the intensity of the field power, electroporation can be reversible or irreversible (cell membrane discharge).

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